

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of supervision on nurse performance at Bahteramas general hospital, southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia

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GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 13(03), 187–192

Publication history: Received on 15 November 2022; revised on 25 December 2022; accepted on 27 December 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2022.13.3.0374>

Abstract

The findings in the initial study found that one of the causes of the low performance of health services in hospitals is the lack of supervision of the work of nurses in carrying out office duties during working hours at the hospital. Supervision in question is the supervision activity carried out by the appointed work supervisor, to supervise the implementation of tasks that are the responsibility of the nurse in the hospital. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of supervision on nurse performance at the Bahteramas General Hospital. The type of research used is quantitative research using a cross sectional study design. The size of the population in this study were 209 people, with a sample size of 138 respondents. As for the method of data collection, it was carried out using interviews and field observations. Implementation Data analysis was carried out using Univariate and Bivariate methods. The results showed that there was an effect of supervision on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital with a p (0.000 <0.05). Conclusion; monitoring variables affect the performance of nurses. Suggestion; The need to increase regular and periodic supervision to ensure that every work that has been done by nurses is in accordance with procedures set by the hospital.

Keywords: Performance; Nurses; Hospitals; Supervision

1. Introduction

Good human resource management is reflected in the achievement of good employee performance good for companies, to achieve maximum performance requires several aspects that must be carried out by the company or organization so that the success of a company or organization can be achieved with good human resource performance and can achieve the goals set by the company or organization. The performance of employees or human resources in an organization or company is inseparable from the influences that exist inside and outside the organization or company, if we look at the factors within the organization that affect employee performance including supervision and work discipline [1]

Human resources is an important part in every agency in achieving its goals, both short-term goals and long-term goals. Therefore, each institution must have qualified human resources. To achieve this goal, every agency must always strive to improve the performance of its employees. Good performance for the agency depends on its human resources [2]

Health service quality assurance or *quality assurance in health care* is a very important and fundamental approach or effort in providing health services to patients. Health care professionals, both individuals and groups, must always strive to provide the best quality health services to all patients without exception [3].

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In this era of globalization, competition is getting tighter in the health sector, which is one of the most important and necessary business fields, because without good health, it will be difficult for every human being to carry out daily activities. The hospital is a service for the community in the health sector for service providers who will provide good services for public health. Along with people's increasing concern for their health, the community's demands for the quality of health services provided by hospitals, especially in terms of nursing [4]

Hospitals are one of the service centers for health, hospitals are required to provide good service to all people who take advantage of this health facility. One of the factors that can be seen by the hospital by providing good service. Medical personnel have a big role to play in determining the success of the hospital because for 24 hours medical personnel play an important role in dealing with patient health problems on an ongoing basis [4]

Supervision has an influence on work productivity. Because with good work supervision, work will run smoothly and produce optimal work results and good supervision will encourage employees to be more active at work and produce good work, especially when completing work with enthusiasm which greatly influences employee work productivity. 5]

Preliminary studies conducted by researchers found that, one of the reasons for the low performance of health services at the Bahteramas Hospital in Southeast Sulawesi Province is the lack of supervision of the work of nurses by the leadership in carrying out office duties during working hours at the hospital. So that the work achievements of nurses are not properly monitored in carrying out these tasks. The supervision in question is routine supervision of the implementation of the work of nurses in accordance with the standard operating procedures that apply at the Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

If you look at the document record of achieving minimum service standards at Bahteramas Hospital, it shows that some of the programs that have been carried out have not yet reached the Minimum Service Standards (SPM). Determined namely customer satisfaction in the Emergency Department (34.0%) from standard $\geq 70\%$, outpatient satisfaction (73.21%) from standard $\geq 90\%$, inpatient satisfaction 60.89% from standard $\geq 90\%$ [6].

Based on the above data, there is a need for research on the effect of nurse supervision on nurse performance at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province. The research objective was to determine the effect of nurse supervision on the performance of nurses at the Bahteramas Regional General Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province.

2. Methodology

The type of research used is quantitative research using a *cross-sectional study design*. The size of the population in this study were 209 people, with a sample size of 138 respondents. As for the method of data collection, it was carried out using interviews and field observations. Implementation Data analysis was carried out using Univariate and Bivariate methods.

3. Research Results

3.1. Analysis of Uni Variate

3.1.1. Supervision

Work supervision as a process of monitoring, observing, and correcting all nursing service actions that have been carried out by nurses in health services, to monitor how far the nursing service process can be carried out by nurses according to operational standards set by the home sick. Supervision of nurses' work is carried out by a work team appointed by the hospital. The distribution of respondents according to the work supervision of nurses is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Shows that out of 138 respondents, the majority of nurses have good work supervision high, namely 92 respondents (66.7%) compared to nurses who have low supervision, namely 46 respondents (33.3%)

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents according to the work supervision of nurses at Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

No.	Work Supervision	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	High	92	66.7
2.	Low	46	33.3
Total		138	100

Source: Primary data, 2022

3.1.2. Performance

Performance is the achievement of work performed by nurses in completing work based on the main tasks and functions that have been determined by law applicable laws at the Bahteramas General Hospital. The distribution of respondents according to nurse discipline at the Bahteramas Hospital in Southeast Sulawesi Province is presented in table 2;

Table 2 The distribution of respondents according to nurse discipline at the Bahteramas Hospital in Southeast Sulawesi Province is presented in table 2;

No.	Performance	Total (n)	Percentage (%)
1.	High	94	68.1
2.	Low	44	31.9
Total		138	100

Source: Primary data, 2022

Table 2 shows that, out of a total of 138 respondents, most of them had high performance, namely 94 respondents (68.1%) compared to nurses who had low performance, namely 44 respondents (31.9%)

3.2. The Effect of Supervision on the Performance of Nurses at Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

The effect of supervision on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas Hospital is presented in table 3.

Table 3 Analysis of the Effect of Supervision on Nurse Performance at Bahteramas Hospital, Southeast Sulawesi Province

Supervision of	Nurse Performance				Total		p Value
	High		Low		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
High	82	89.1	10	10.2	92	100	0.000
Low	12	26.1	34	73.9	46	100	
Total	94	68.1	44	31.9	138	100	

Source: Primary data, 2022

Table 3 shows that of the 92 respondents (100%) who have high supervision there are more nurses who have high performance, namely 82 respondents (89.1 %) compared ng nurses who have low performance as many as 10 respondents (10.2%). Meanwhile, of the 46 respondents (100%) who had low supervision, there were fewer nurses who had high performance, namely 12 respondents (26.1%), compared to nurses who had low performance, namely 34 respondents (73.9%). Chi square test results the value of $p = 0.000$ ($p > 0.05$) means that H_0 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant influence between supervision on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital in Southeast Sulawesi Provinc.

4. Discussion

Nurses as one of the health workers in hospitals play an important role in efforts to achieve health development goals. The success of health services depends on the participation of nurses in providing quality care for patients [7]. Considering that nurses are the most important resource in running a hospital without minimizing the meaning of other human resources, nurses are required to have intellectual, interpersonal, technical and moral abilities. This aims to maintain and improve quality health services. Nurses provide services in the hospital 24 hours a day, and have constant contact with patients. Therefore nursing services in hospitals are an integral part of health services. The contribution made by nurses greatly determines the quality of service in hospitals. Thus efforts to improve hospital services must be followed by efforts to improve the quality of nursing services [8].

One of the employee coaching can be done with supervision. In carrying out company management, supervision is needed so that the duties and functions of each division run properly [9]. Supervision is carried out for the smooth running of the organization and to determine whether organizational goals can be achieved or not. According to [10] the purpose of implementing supervision is to find out the implementation of the plan, to find out the difficulties that exist, to anticipate obstacles, and to find a way out if there are obstacles

Human resources are one of the internal factors that play an important role in determining the success or failure an organization in achieving goals. Organizations that have quality human resources will become an organization that is able to compete and excel because it will produce high performance. Human resources are the most important resource owned by an organization, one of the implications is that the most important investment that may be made by an organization is in the field of human resources [11]

The research findings in table 1 show that, generally nurses who state high supervision, more in number than nurses who stated low supervision. This shows that the higher the supervision, the higher the performance of nurses in completing the work that is their responsibility in health services. On the other hand, the lower the supervision, the lower the performance level of nurses in completing the work they are responsible for in health services. This is because in the assumption that nurses, they must be aware of their duties and responsibilities as servants of the state and servants of the community, to provide quality health services and satisfy customers is a manifestation of their responsibilities as state civil servants. Thus, in relation to the main tasks and additional duties of nurses they have carried out so far, they have become a top priority in their lives, apart from prioritizing their responsibilities in household matters. It is this drive and goal that always encourages them to be more active in providing health services according to their function, because their service as civil servants is one of the main sources of family income.

Human resources are a very important asset in an organization or company, therefore human resources must be managed properly so that the goals of the organization or company can be achieved effectively and efficiently in an organization to contribute more in a strategically responsible way [12]

Work force supervisors, errors and omissions have not occurred in the work of nurses, supervision mechanisms have not been properly complied with, and supervision is sometimes carried out informally. Thus, so far the implementation of the nurse's work has not been properly monitored to ensure that the quality of the nurse's work while on duty in daily life, maintains that the implementation of tasks is in accordance with the applicable plans and regulations, controls that the management of nursing services is carried out as it should, and the nurse has carried out her duties as well as possible, to develop understanding and skills in work, to receive information and other perspectives about one's work, to provide good support in work.

In the supervision of nursing services, generally the head of the hospital room as a manager is given the task of supervising to monitor and evaluate the performance of nursing staff in accordance with the responsibilities they carry. The duties and responsibilities are in the form of regulation and control of nursing service activities in hospital inpatient rooms. A supervisor must have good skills and abilities as a planner, coach, director, controller, trainer, observer, assessor and regulator of nursing services. Therefore, another benefit of supervision is coaching for nursing staff who are negligent or have made mistakes at work, so that with this coaching it will add insight to nurses so that they continue to be disciplined and obedient to the implementation of standard operating procedures for nursing actions to prevent further errors in service.

Awareness of the importance of having quality human resources, in this case nurses, needs to be followed up with various strategies that can improve the quality of nurses. One that is measured in the quality of nurse performance is the problem of discipline. Work discipline is a tool used by managers to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change an effort to increase one's awareness and willingness to comply with all applicable social rules and

norms. Factors that influence work discipline are goals and abilities, human relations, remuneration, fairness, legal sanctions, exemplary leadership and firmness [13].

Generally, the implementation of nursing work supervision in health services is aimed at service quality and remains the managerial responsibility of the hospital. Likewise, the achievement of the success of nursing work supervision is largely determined by the quality of the field supervisor. Supervisory officials are generally the direct superiors of nursing staff including hospital directors, hospital service directors, heads of medical services, heads of service sections and heads of hospital nursing service rooms. Supervision is needed to develop understanding and skills at work, to receive information and other perspectives about one's work, to support both personal and work aspects, to ensure that individuals can work in a disciplined manner, to explore and express distress, personal restimulation, transference that work may bring, planning and better utilization of resources and professionals, ensuring the quality of work and ensuring good health care for customers.

The results of the chi square test obtained a value of $p = 0.000$ ($p > 0.05$) meaning that H_0 is accepted. This shows that there is a significant influence between supervision on the performance of nurses at Bahteramas General Hospital in Southeast Sulawesi Province. The results of this study are in line with the results of research [14] which states that supervision has a positive effect on work productivity. The results of the study [15] say that supervision has an influence on employee performance. The results of the study [16] said that there was an influence of supervision on the performance of the employees of the Anjir Muara Health Center, Barito Kuala Regency. The results of the study [4] say that there is an effect of work supervision on employee performance at Karya Husada Cikampek Hospital. The results of the study [17] say that supervision has a positive influence on work productivity. The results of research [2] say that supervision has a positive influence on work productivity. The results of the study [18] say that supervision has a positive influence on work productivity. The results of the study [19] say that Supervision partially has a significant effect on the performance of Pelindo IV Pantoloan employees. The results of the study [20] say that supervision has a positive influence on work productivity. The results of the study [1] say that supervision has a positive influence on work productivity.

Attention to improving the performance of nurses in providing nursing services in hospitals is a very basic demand, because these factors can shape the performance of nurses in hospitals so as to support the implementation of their duties and responsibilities in providing nursing services. If this does not receive enough attention and is left without proper handling efforts, it is feared that it will have an impact on the success of improving the quality of health worker resources, especially in providing nursing services in hospitals [8]. One of the elements that has a large role and greatly determines the quality of hospital health services is nurses, this is because the nursing profession has a relatively large proportion, which almost exceeds 50% of all hospital human resources and interacts the most directly with patients. Work and duties more than other staff, because the nature and function of this staff is to support medical services in the form of nursing services known as nursing care [21].

5. Conclusion

Monitoring variables affect the performance of nurses. Suggestion; The need to increase regular and periodic supervision to ensure that every job that has been done by nurses is in accordance with the procedures set by the hospital.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank the Dean of the Faculty of Public Health, Halu Oleo University, who has provided support to the writing team so that this research can be carried out properly. Furthermore, the team of authors would like to thank all those who have helped until the end of this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors in the making of this scientific article have no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

All informants/respondents involved in this study have stated their consent as informants/respondents to be interviewed and provided information/information in accordance with research needs.

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